

Can Personal KG-based RAG Empower Patients?

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Abstract. The European Health Data Space (EHDS) sets out regulations for the management of electronic health data, distinguishing between its primary use in direct healthcare and patient data portability, and its secondary use for research, innovation, and policy-making. We aim to empower individuals to take control of their health by enhancing personal health data management. In this work, we discuss the challenges in electronic personal health data access and propose developing a system that leverages personal health knowledge graphs and retrieval-augmented generation to ensure FAIR personal electronic health data representation and personalized health information delivery.

Keywords: Personal Knowledge Graph · Retrieval-Augmented Generation · Health

1 Introduction

The European Health Data Space (EHDS) proposal¹ establishes regulations for the management of electronic health data, distinguishing between its primary use in direct healthcare and patient data portability, and its secondary use for research, innovation, and policy-making. Notably, the regulation requires electronic health record systems to support interoperability. Several ongoing European projects align with EHDS [3] by developing platforms for individuals to access and manage their health data, including AIDAVA² and Gravitare Health³.

Research indicates that accessing personal electronic health data enhances patient engagement [6], understanding, and communication [2]. However, usability challenges, low health literacy, and accessibility barriers hinder the wide-spread adoption of Personal Health Records (PHRs) [8], highlighting the need for innovative personal health data management strategies.

In this paper, we discuss the challenges associated with accessing electronic personal health data and propose an EHDS-compliant system based on personal health knowledge graphs (PHKGs) and retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) to

¹ Regulation (EU) 2025/327 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 February 2025 on the European Health Data Space and amending Directive 2011/24/EU and Regulation (EU) 2024/2847.

² <https://www.aidava.eu/>

³ <https://www.gravitarehealth.eu/>

enable personalized access. Our goal is to enable individuals to manage their health by representing personal electronic health data according to FAIR principles and delivering accurate, comprehensible personalized health information through user-centered multi-turn dialog systems.

2 Challenges

According to the EHDS⁴, personal electronic health data includes health-related information, such as genetic data and healthcare service records. This data should be accessible to individuals, allowing them to view, share, and manage their own health information. Table 1 details current key limitations to accessing personal health data, along with solutions and their expected impact.

Table 1: Overview of limitations, solutions, and impact in personal health data access.

Problem	Limitations	Solutions	Impact
Lack of data ownership	Institutional-centric data control	Decentralized data systems, such as blockchain or SOLID	User-controlled ownership
Risks in data privacy and sharing	No fine-grained access to data	Decentralized data systems with certificate authorities for access control	Granular data sharing
Poor data interoperability	Fragmented and siloed data	Adoption of global interoperability standards	Facilitated data access
Low health search relevance	Lack of personalized health information	Retrieval systems with integrated personal health data access	Better health information access
Insufficient transparency in data access	Obscure data provenance	Provenance metadata tracking, such as source identifiers and timestamps	Auditability, Trust
Poor health literacy	Complex clinical language	Conversational interfaces	Understanding

3 Proposal

We propose a RAG system that uses personal knowledge graphs (PKG) to organize and retrieve personal health data, enabling personalized access to health data and supporting individuals in managing their health. Figure 1 presents the system pipeline with a practical example of user interaction. Figure 1a shows the process of users querying the system, which retrieves relevant data from the users’ PHKG to generate responses using a large language model (LLM). Figure 1b illustrates a multi-turn dialog: the first query retrieves biopsy results from the PHKG, while the second requests definitions and personalized explanations.

⁴ Article 2(2) of Regulation (EU) 2025/327.

Fig. 1: A personal health knowledge graph-based RAG system.

3.1 PKGs for Personal Health Data Representation

A PKG is a knowledge graph in which an individual has control over writing and sharing data that is personal to them within the graph [10]. In the healthcare domain, PHKGs are used to semantically represent personal health data, creating an individual’s detailed health profile [13]. PHKGs are flexible in representing and updating information, making it easier for individuals to add or modify facts within their own PHKG. Although relational databases also allow data updates, they rely on rigid schemas that might require restructuring to integrate new relationships. As a result, individuals may be restricted in the types of data they can add or update, depending on the limitations of the database schema.

The EHDS proposal seeks to make electronic health data FAIR—Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. Structuring personal electronic health data as PHKGs supports this objective by providing semantic data representation that enables discoverability and machine-readability, while also facilitating integration with knowledge organizing systems such as ICD-10 and SNOMED CT and interoperability resources like HL7 FHIR⁵. Modular ontologies in PHKG design further allow for data reuse, adaptation, and personalized control over data ownership, allowing individuals to selectively share specific components of their PHKG.

Semantically structuring data in knowledge graphs also improves the interpretability and effectiveness of information retrieval by enabling multi-hop reasoning across entities and relationships, rather than query-to-document matching [7,14]. PKGs further enhance personalization by supporting user-specific information retrieval. Liu et al. [5] developed a PKG-based question-answering assistant that integrates data from various mobile applications to answer complex user-specific questions. Pilot studies demonstrate that fine-tuning GPT models with PHKGs enables reliable retrieval of specific health information from diverse sources [12].

⁵ <https://hl7.org/fhir/>

3.2 Interacting with Personal Electronic Health Data

Simply providing access to personal electronic health data does not guarantee understanding, as low health literacy, challenges in usability, and accessibility in accessing personal electronic health data can prevent individuals from effectively managing their health information. Systems must go beyond providing access to data and focus on comprehensively meeting individuals' information needs. Multi-turn dialog systems address these barriers by enabling iterative, conversational interactions, allowing users to ask follow-up questions, request clarifications, and receive personalized information [9]. Unlike traditional search systems, which provide static answers, multi-turn dialog systems maintain conversational continuity and adapt to user needs, making interactions more supportive.

Recent advances in multi-turn dialog systems use LLMs [4]. However, LLMs are prone to hallucinating and providing factual inconsistencies. To increase their accuracy and reliability, external integration methods use RAG or knowledge graphs to leverage external information retrieval and reasoning. Upadhyay et al. [11] enhanced the retrieval of topically relevant and factually accurate health information using a RAG approach, aiding in the prevention of health misinformation. However, RAGs do not ensure that LLMs use trusted knowledge bases for their answers, and over-reliance on retrieved content can propagate bias or inaccuracies if the knowledge bases are incomplete or missing data [1]. To maintain user trust, it is important to implement guardrails. The system should transparently indicate when it lacks an answer due to no retrieved results, prompt users to clarify or reformulate ambiguous queries, and address incorrect retrievals.

By integrating RAG with PHKGs, health information delivery becomes more personalized, allowing users to interact with and interpret their own data in contextually relevant ways. We will evaluate the system through iterative prototyping and user testing conducted in two phases: 1) co-creation sessions using a small set of questions will allow users to add, modify or remove dialog turns and suggest new topics, and 2) feedback loops will assess the naturalness and correctness of responses. Insights will be used to refine the system by adjusting prompting strategies, retrieval methods, or guardrails as needed.

4 Conclusion

In conclusion, we discussed challenges related to the access, ownership, interoperability, and usability of personal electronic health data. We also proposed an EHDS-compliant system that integrates PHKGs with RAG and multi-turn dialog interfaces to support FAIR, user-centered, and personalized health information delivery while prioritizing data ownership and interoperability.

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